

STATISTICAL MODELLING OF f_t TO PROCESS PARAMETERS IN 30 NM GATE LENGTH FINFETs

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the effect of process variations on unity gain frequency (f_t) in 30 nm gate length FinFET by performing extensive TCAD simulations. Six different geometrical parameters, channel doping, source/drain doping and gate electrode work function are studied for their sensitivity on f_t . It is found that f_t is more sensitive to gate length, underlap, gate-oxide thickness, channel and Source/Drain doping and less sensitive to source/drain width and length, and work function variations. Statistical modelling has been performed for f_t through design of experiment with respect to sensitive parameters. The model has been validated through a comparison between random set of experimental data simulations and predicted values obtained from the model.

KEYWORDS

f_t , FinFET, process variations, Statistical modelling, Design of Experiments

1. INTRODUCTION

The progress in CMOS technology has made it well suited for RF and microwave operations at high level of integration [1], and the continuous improvement of the device performance has made it a contender for low-power and, eventually, low-cost radio front end. In the area of multi-gate transistors, double-gate FinFETs are considered a serious contender for channel scaling [2], [3] because of their quasi-planar structure and the compatibility with CMOS. Several authors have already studied the low field mobility in fins of various widths [4]-[6]. RF performance of FinFETs is reported in [7], [8].

Unity gain frequency (f_t) is one of the important metric in RF applications. f_t is defined as the frequency at which the current gain of the device becomes unity. f_t is calculated by

$$f_t = \frac{g_m}{2\pi C_{gg}} \quad (1)$$

where C_{gg} is the combination of C_{gs} , C_{gd} , overlap capacitance and any other fringing capacitance. In this article, nine different geometrical parameters related to FinFET are varied to capture their sensitivity on f_t .

This paper analyzes double-gate FinFETs as a downscaling option for CMOS technology from an RF perspective. The effect of various structural and doping parameters (9 parameters in total) on f_t is studied and the five most sensitive parameters are identified. Using these sensitive parameters a 5 point DOE (design of experiments) is designed and the simulations are done. i.e. this work is based on design and simulation of the nominal device, design of experiment and running of the experiment, extraction of results, fitting the response surfaces (models) and testing of the models. We have modelled f_t in terms of the most sensitive parameters like gate

length, underlap, gate oxide thickness, channel and source/drain doping. The model that describe these quantities have an approximated form [9] as,

$$y = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + b_4x_4 + b_5x_5 + b_{11}x_1^2 + b_{22}x_2^2 + b_{33}x_3^2 + b_{44}x_4^2 + b_{55}x_5^2 + b_{12}x_1x_2 + b_{13}x_1x_3 + b_{14}x_1x_4 + b_{15}x_1x_5 + b_{23}x_2x_3 + b_{24}x_2x_4 + b_{25}x_2x_5 + b_{34}x_3x_4 + b_{35}x_3x_5 + b_{45}x_4x_5 \quad (2)$$

where x_1 is the gate length, x_2 is the underlap, x_3 is the gate oxide thickness, x_4 is the channel doping and x_5 is the Source/Drain doping, y is the unity gain frequency, b 's are the fitting parameters determined by the data obtained from the experiment. Next section deals with the simulation methodology followed in this paper. Section III discusses the simulation results and statistical modelling. Finally section IV provides conclusions.

2. SIMULATION METHODOOGY

Sentaurus TCAD simulator from Synopsys [10] is used to perform all the simulations. This simulator has many modules and the following are used in this study.

- Sentaurus structure editor (SDE): To create the device structure, to define doping, to define contacts, and to generate mesh for device simulation
- Sentaurus device simulator (SDEVICE): To perform all DC and AC simulations
- Inspect and Tecplot: To view the results.

The physics section of SDEVICE includes the appropriate models for band to band tunnelling, quantization of inversion layer charge, doping dependency of mobility, effect of high and normal electric fields on mobility, and velocity saturation. The structure generated from SDE is shown in Fig 1. Doping and mesh information can also be observed in Fig. 1. Figure 2 shows the schematic diagram of the device. Totally nine different parameters are considered in this study. Out of them, six are geometrical parameters - gate length (L_g), underlap (L_{un}), fin width (W), source/drain width (SW), source/drain length (SL), and T_{ox} and these are shown in Fig. 2. Other three parameters are channel doping (N_{ch}), source/drain doping (N_{SD}) and gate electrode work function (WF). The various process parameters considered in this study and their range are given in Table. 1. Table 1 also gives the dimensions of the nominal device. Standard AC simulations are done in SDEVICE and f_t is extracted from these results. f_t is the frequency at which $|Y_{21}/Y_{11}|$ equals one, and it strongly depends on the gate bias. At various gate biases f_t is calculated and the maximum of them is taken as f_t . Supply voltage (V_{dd}) used in this study is 0.8 V.

Figure 1. Structure of the Dual-Gate FinFET

Figure 2. Schematic view of Dual-Gate FinFET

Table 1. Characteristics of the device

Process parameter	Nominal value	Range
Gate length (L_g)	30 nm	20 nm to 40 nm
Underlap (L_{un})	3 nm	1 nm to 8 nm
Fin Width (W)	4 nm	2 nm to 7 nm
Source Length (SL)	15 nm	10 nm to 20 nm
Source Width (SW)	8 nm	4 nm to 16 nm
Channel Doping (N_{ch})	$1 \times 10^{16}/\text{cm}^3$	$1 \times 10^{15}/\text{cm}^3$ to $1 \times 10^{19}/\text{cm}^3$
Source Drain Doping (N_{SD})	$1 \times 10^{20}/\text{cm}^3$	$1 \times 10^{18}/\text{cm}^3$ to $2 \times 10^{20}/\text{cm}^3$
Oxide Thickness (T_{ox})	1 nm	0.5 nm to 2 nm
Gate Work Function (WF)	4.337 eV	4.13 eV to 4.9 eV

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Sensitivity Analysis of Process Parameters

The nine different process parameters are varied one at a time, according to the range given in Table 1 and their sensitivity to f_t is analysed in this section.

3.1.1 Variation in Gate Length

Figure 3 shows the variation of f_t against L_g . It can be observed from Fig. 3 that f_t initially increases and then decreases. As per (1), f_t is decided by both g_m and C_{gg} . While g_m degrades with L_g , C_{gg} shows a different behaviour i.e. initially decreases with L_g and then increases (Fig 4). The initial decrease of C_{gg} can be attributed to the reduction of C_{gd} [11]. At some point, C_{gs} starts dominating and calls for the increase in C_{gg} . The combined behaviour of g_m and C_{gg} contributes to the variation of f_t w.r.t. L_g .

Figure 3. Variation of f_t with respect to L_g

Figure 4. Variation of C_{gs} with respect to L_g

3.1.2. Variation in Underlap

Figure 5 depicts the plot between f_t and L_{un} . It can be seen from Fig 5 that f_t initially increases and then decreases w.r.t. L_{un} . Increasing L_{un} reduces the fringing capacitance, and thereby decreases C_{gg} [12], [13]. The C_{gg} in DGMOS can be expressed as

$$C_{gg} = \text{Series}(C_{ox}, C_{si}) \parallel C_{ov} \parallel C_{fringing} \quad (3)$$

where C_{ox} is the oxide capacitance, C_{si} is the silicon body capacitance, C_{ov} is the gate to source/drain overlap capacitance and $C_{fringing}$ is the fringing capacitance and is given by

$$C_{fringing} = \frac{WK\epsilon_{di}}{\pi} \ln \frac{\pi W}{\sqrt{L_{un}^2 + T_{ox}^2}} e^{-\left| \frac{L_{un} - T_{ox}}{L_{un} + T_{ox}} \right|} \quad (4)$$

When L_{un} increases current degrades and thereby g_m monotonically decreases. The combined behavior of g_m and C_{gg} is responsible for the f_t trend seen in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Variation of f_t with respect to L_{un}

3.1.3 .Variation in Fin Width

When W is varied we may either face volume inversion or may not, depending upon the channel doping levels. When the channel doping is $1 \times 10^{16}/\text{cm}^3$ volume inversion is not seen [14]. Therefore, the increase in W increases current and thereby g_m and f_t . Figure 6 shows this kind of behaviour between f_t and W . For the channel doping around $1.5 \times 10^{18}/\text{cm}^3$, volume inversion effect is seen which causes f_t to decrease initially and then to increase w.r.t W . This is depicted in Fig. 7.

Figure 6. Variation of f_t w.r.t W without volume inversion

Figure 7. Variation of f_t w.r.t W with volume inversion

3.1.4. Variation in Source Length

Figure 8 shows the f_t versus source length plot. Increasing source length increases the parasitic resistance associated with the channel and degrades g_m which in turn decreases f_t .

Figure 8. Variation of f_t with respect to SL

3.1.5 .Variation in Source Width

Figure 9 shows f_t as a function of source width. It can be noticed from Fig. 9 that f_t is almost independent of SW.

Figure 9. Variation of f_t with respect to SW

3.1.6 .Variation in Oxide Thickness

Figure 10 shows the variation of f_t with T_{ox} . f_t increases initially w.r.t T_{ox} . Both g_m and C_{gg} together control f_t . C_{gg} always decreases when T_{ox} increases whereas g_m may go down or high depending on whether we are driven by short channel effects or not. The combined effect of g_m and C_{gg} decides f_t behaviour with respect to T_{ox} .

Figure 10. Variation of f_t with respect to T_{ox}

3.1.7 .Variation in Channel Doping

Figure 11 shows the variation of f_t against N_{ch} . Threshold voltage of DGFET/FinFET is insensitive up to $1 \times 10^{17}/\text{cm}^3$ [15]. From which it can be reasoned out that f_t is also insensitive at lower channel doping levels. The same is seen in Fig. 11. At higher doping levels, f_t decreases due to g_m degradation.

Figure 11. Variation of f_t with respect to N_{ch} .

3.1.8 .Variation in Source/drain Doping

Figure 12 shows the variation of f_t with source/drain doping. When N_{SD} increases I_{on} and g_m increase due to the lowered parasitic series resistance values, and thereby f_t increases. This is reflected in Fig.12

Figure 12. Variation of f_t with respect to N_{SD}

3.1.9 .Variation in Work Function

High frequency characteristics are less sensitive to work function variation [16]. Therefore, f_t is expected to be indifferent to gate electrode work function. Figure 13 shows f_t versus gate work function plot and it can be noticed that f_t exhibits a flat behaviour w.r.t work function.

Figure 13. Variation of f_t with respect to WF

3.2 Statistical modelling:

The sensitive parameters are chosen as L_g , L_{un} , T_{ox} , N_{ch} and N_{SD} . These sensitive parameters are made to undergo a variability study with the help of design of experiments. The range of these sensitive parameters for the variability study is given in Table 2 which results in 2500 simulations. The model that has been obtained by the regression technique is generated with the help of SPSS [17]. The regression coefficients for the second order polynomial of the process parameters are shown in Table 3.

Table 2 .Range of Sensitive Parameters

Process parameters	Range	Points in the range
Gate length (L_g)	20 nm to 40 nm	20, 25, 30, 35 and 40 (nm)
Underlap (L_{un})	1nm to 9 nm	1,3, 5,7 and 9 (nm)
Oxide Thickness (T_{ox})	0.5 nm to 2.2 nm	0.5, 1,1.2,2 and 2.2 (nm)
Channel Doping (N_{ch})	$1 \times 10^{16} / \text{cm}^3$ to $1 \times 10^{19} / \text{cm}^3$	1×10^{16} , 1×10^{17} , 1×10^{18} and $1 \times 10^{19} / \text{cm}^3$
Source Drain Doping (N_{SD})	$5 \times 10^{18} / \text{cm}^3$ to $2 \times 10^{20} / \text{cm}^3$	5×10^{18} , 5×10^{19} , 9.5×10^{19} , 1.1×10^{20} and $2 \times 10^{20} / \text{cm}^3$

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Table 3. Process parameters along with their corresponding regression coefficients

Factor	Coefficient	Factor values
Constant	b_0	2.765E12
L_g	b_1	-1.103E20
L_{un}	b_2	-3.964E19
T_{ox}	b_3	4.007E19
N_{ch}	b_4	-.052
N_{SD}	b_5	.009
L_g^2	b_{11}	1.164E27
L_{un}^2	b_{22}	-4.210E27
T_{ox}^2	b_{33}	-3.564E28
N_{ch}^2	b_{44}	9.698E-16
N_{SD}^2	b_{55}	-1.489E-17
$L_g L_{un}$	b_{12}	1.874E27
$L_g T_{ox}$	b_{13}	1.639E27
$L_g N_{ch}$	b_{14}	1266894.540
$L_g N_{SD}$	b_{15}	-100967.539
$L_{un} T_{ox}$	b_{23}	7.137E27
$L_{un} N_{ch}$	b_{24}	-3105744.884
$L_{un} N_{SD}$	b_{25}	-124191.069
$T_{ox} N_{ch}$	b_{34}	-1672454.265
$T_{ox} N_{SD}$	b_{35}	23534.568
$N_{ch} N_{SD}$	b_{45}	-4.254E-17

In order to study the statistical nature of the device output with respect to sensitive parameters, we have generated 3^5 (=243) uniformly distributed pseudo-random numbers for each of these sensitive parameters and f_t values are predicted from the generated model. For the same set of random numbers generated, TCAD simulations are carried out and the f_t values are extracted. To have a correlation plot TCAD values are plotted against model values and the same is depicted in Fig. 14. The correlation coefficient is found out as $r=0.992$.

Fig. 14: Correlation plot between TCAD simulated data and model predicted data for f_t . Correlation coefficient r is depicted here

4. CONCLUSION

Six geometrical parameters (L_g , L_{un} , W , SW , SL , and T_{ox}), and three non-geometrical parameters (N_{ch} , N_{SD} , and WF) have been varied over a range and their effect on f_t have been studied through TCAD simulations. It was found that L_g , L_{un} , T_{ox} , N_{ch} and N_{SD} are more sensitive parameters whereas gate electrode work function, source/drain length and width are less sensitive parameters. By running DOE using the sensitive parameters in TCAD, statistical modelling has been performed. Correlation coefficient around 0.992 was got while running the simulations with random set of values for sensitive parameters.

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